

Supplementary Material 1

Regression methods comparisons

To evaluate the potential impact of regression method choice on ventilatory control parameters (particularly β -slope), we compared four approaches applied to the VE- $P_{ET}CO_2$ relationship for both groups:

1. Objective threshold-based (VE+2SD): Regression on data points exceeding the resting mean VE+2SD ;
2. Visual threshold estimation: Regression starting from a visually selected breakpoint ;
3. Segmented (piecewise) regression: breakpoint optimized to maximize model fit ;
4. Read method : Linear regression from the onset of CO₂ inhalation to the end of the test (preserving time sequence) (1).

Summary of comparative findings

Method	Mean Adjusted R² ± SD	Statistically inferior to Read
VE+2SD	0.575 ± 0.23	p < 0.001
Visual threshold	0.630 ± 0.20	p = 0.030
Segmented regression	0.587 ± 0.22	p = 0.003
Read method	0.794 ± 0.12	-

Mean adjusted R² was higher in the Read method and a repeated-measures ANOVA showed significant differences in adjusted R² among the first three methods compared with the Read method, which was confirmed with the appropriate Friedman test.

(1) Read DC. A clinical method for assessing the ventilatory response to carbon dioxide. *Australas Ann Med* 16:20–32, 1967. doi: 10.1111/imj.1967.16.1.20.
